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Sustainable alternatives to thermoset polymers for aerospace composites: a comparison using LCA

Andrea Bologna, Antonio Mattia Grande

Department of Aerospace Science and Technology (DAER), Politecnico di Milano

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- Introduction
- What is LCA?
- Scope definition
- Case study
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- LCA results
- Conclusions

Introduction: European policies framework

- Aviation makes up for 13.9% of transport emissions and it's responsible for 4% of total EU GHG emissions [1]
- Emissions produced by general aviation could triple by 2050 according to ICAO [2]
- ICAO drew a resolution to decarbonise aerospace industry with sustainable market-based measures [2]
- EASA drew the European Aviation Environmental Report, one of the chapters is dedicated to technology and design [3]

Introduction: AAM market expectations

Total equivalent CO₂ emissions of a traditional aircraft life cycle:

- >99% from the use phase
- <1% from production and EoL [4]

What about UAM?

Market value forecast of 74 billion USD in the US for civil EVTOLs in 2035 [5]

Shorter lifecycle

Higher environmental impact from production and EoL: ranging from 20% to 75% according to different scenarios [6], [7]

$m \approx 10^{4/5} \text{ kg}$

$m \approx 10^3 \text{ kg}$

What is LCA?

LCA phases:

- 1) Goal and scope definition
- 2) LCI (Life Cycle Inventory)
- 3) LCIA (Life Cycle Impact Assessment)
- 4) Interpretation of the results

Scope definition:

Carry out a **preliminary comparison between different polymeric matrices**, analysing the Global Warming Potential associated to the production and EoL phases of an EVTOL.

Polymeric matrix	Characteristics
Thermoset resin	Epoxy resin is considered the standard solution in aerospace industry.
High-performance thermoplastics	Like the ketone family (PEEK, PEKK, etc.), high mechanical performance and chemical stability, offers the possibility to be reshaped.
Covalent adaptable networks	Similar to thermoset resins, but through a certain stimulus they can be reshaped. Still at research stage.

Case study

Functional unit: EVTOL structure, mass = **1465.5 kg**

Assumptions:

- The same fibers are used for all the matrices
- The use phase is neglected since the performance of the aircraft is expected to be similar in all cases
- The small difference in terms of performance is difficult to quantify

credits: NASA

Mass fraction for each material [7]

	Aluminium	Steel	Titanium	Carbon fiber	Glass fiber	Polymeric Matrix
Mass fraction	0.173	0.093	0.066	0.294	0.119	0.256

Thermoset resin:

- Autoclave curing
- Mechanical recycling: industry adopted best option

Thermoplastic matrix:

- Production by thermoforming
- EoL mix of recycling and reshaping

Vitrimer:

- Production like thermoset
- EoL like thermoplastic

LCA results: GWP 1/2

- Results obtained using the ReCiPe 2016 method
- The lowest CO₂ emissions can be achieved with vitrimers
- The percentage of reused material strongly impact the GWP
- Thermoset resin results as the worst option in all the considered scenarios

	Thermoplastic	Vitrimer
Avoided emissions	10.9%	20.8%

- PEEK production produces more emissions with respect to thermoset resins
- Most of the GWP comes from energy production

Looking at Cumulative Energy Demand (CED) it is clear that composites material request the highest energy for they production, which can be strongly mitigated by reuse strategies

LCA results: sensitivity analysis

The breakeven point which justifies the adoption of PEEK is obtained when almost 50% of the material is reused.

- Decarbonization is of paramount importance in the aerospace industry
- Looking at new trends, production and EoL will be more relevant
- Reshaping composite materials could give a relevant contribution

Future developments

- The LCA database should be widened with better quality data
- How many times the reshaping can be carried out with limited degradation of the material
- How environmental effects will impact the reshaping possibility and the performance

[1] https://climate.ec.europa.eu/eu-action/transport/reducing-emissions-aviation_en

[2] <https://www.icao.int/environmental-protection/Pages/default.aspx>

[3] <https://www.easa.europa.eu/en/light/topics/european-aviation-environmental-report-2022>

[4] I. Jakovljević, R. Mijailović, and P. Mirosavljević, “Carbon dioxide emission during the life cycle of turbofan aircraft,” *Energy*, vol. 148, pp. 866–875, Apr. 2018, doi: 10.1016/j.energy.2018.02.022.

[5] A. P. Cohen, S. A. Shaheen, and E. M. Farrar, “Urban Air Mobility: History, Ecosystem, Market Potential, and Challenges,” *IEEE Transactions on Intelligent Transportation Systems*, vol. 22, no. 9, pp. 6074–6087, Sep. 2021, doi: 10.1109/TITS.2021.3082767.

[6] R. Arvidsson, A. Nordelöf, and S. Brynolf, “Life cycle assessment of a two-seater all-electric aircraft,” *International Journal of Life Cycle Assessment*, vol. 29, no. 2, pp. 240–254, Feb. 2024, doi: 10.1007/s11367-023-02244-z.

[7] N. André and M. Hajek, “Robust environmental life cycle assessment of electric vtol concepts for urban air mobility,” in *AIAA Aviation 2019 Forum*, American Institute of Aeronautics and Astronautics Inc, AIAA, 2019, pp. 1–14. doi: 10.2514/6.2019-3473.

Andrea Bologna

PhD student at the Department of Aerospace Science and Technology (DAER), Politecnico di Milano

andrea.bologna@polimi.it

Antonio Mattia Grande

Associate professor at the Department of Aerospace Science and Technology (DAER), Politecnico di Milano

antoniomattia.grande@polimi.it

Thank you for the attention!

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Supplementary: LCA processes

Processes with energy cost

Process	Output Mass [kg]	Waste [kg]	ρ [kWh/kg]	P [kW]	t [h]	E [kWh]
CFRP TS						
Prepregging	1083,79		11,10			12030,10
Lay up	867,03	216,76				
Curing	693,63	173,41		6936,27	8,00	55490,17
GFRP TS						
Prepregging	437,85		11,10			4860,16
Lay up	350,28	87,57				
Curing	280,23	70,06		2802,25	8,00	22418,03
CFRP TP						
Prepregging	1205,89		11,10			13385,36
Panel prod.	964,71	241,18	6,10			5884,74
Processing	693,63	271,08				84000,44
GFRP TP						
Prepregging	487,18		11,10			5407,69
Panel prod.	389,74	97,44	6,10			2377,43
Processing	280,23	109,52				33936,18
Aluminium						
Machining	251,59	4780,26		120,00	1673,09	200771,08
Steel						
Machining	135,21	2568,99		120,00	1156,04	138725,21
Titanium						
Machining	95,84	191,69				58733,75

Supplementary: Carbon fibers inventory

Output	Quantity
Carbon fibers	1 Kg
Input	
Polyacrylonitrile fibres (PAN), from acrylonitrile and methacrylate, prod. mix, PAN w/o additives EU-27 S	1 Kg
Electricity, high voltage {DE} market for Cut-off, S	459 MJ/kg
Transport, freight, lorry 16e32 metric ton, euro3 {RER} market for transport, freight, lorry 16e32 metric ton, EURO3 Cut-off, S	2224 kgkm

A. D. La Rosa, S. Greco, C. Tosto, and G. Cicala, “LCA and LCC of a chemical recycling process of waste CF-thermoset composites for the production of novel CF-thermoplastic composites. Open loop and closed loop scenarios,” J Clean Prod, vol. 304, Jul. 2021, doi: 10.1016/j.jclepro.2021.127158.

Supplementary: Mechanical recycling of CFRP

Process	Item	Amount	Unit
Input	Composite	1	kg
	Electricity, medium voltage {IT} electricity voltage transformation from high to medium voltage APOS, S	0.27	MJ
Output	rCF	0.24	kg
	Fine powder	0.19	kg
	Coarse fraction	0.57	kg

M. Wu, J. Sadhukhan, R. Murphy, U. Bharadwaj, and X. Cui, “A novel life cycle assessment and life cycle costing framework for carbon fibre-reinforced composite materials in the aviation industry,” *International Journal of Life Cycle Assessment*, vol. 28, no. 5, pp. 566–589, May 2023, doi: 10.1007/s11367-023-02164-y.

Supplementary: LCI thermosplastic EVTOL

Process	Database	Unit	Quantity
Aluminium (waste treatment) {GLO} recycling of aluminium Cut-off, S	Ecoinvent 3	kg	4780,27
Aluminium, primary, ingot {IAI Area, EU27 & EFTA} market for aluminium, primary, ingot Cut-off, S	Ecoinvent 3	kg	5031,86
Electricity, high voltage {Europe without Switzerland} market group for electricity, high voltage Cut-off, S	Ecoinvent 3	MJ	343772,6
Electricity, medium voltage {RER} market group for electricity, medium voltage Cut-off, S	Ecoinvent 3	MJ	1955599
Glass fibre {RER} glass fibre production Cut-off, S	Ecoinvent 3	kg	302,58
Polyacrylonitrile fibres (PAN), from acrylonitrile and methacrylate, prod. mix, PAN w/o additives EU-27 S	ELCD	kg	748,96
PEEK (Polyetheretherketone)	IDEMAT2025	kg	641,53
Steel and iron (waste treatment) {GLO} recycling of steel and iron Cut-off, S	Ecoinvent 3	kg	2760,68
Steel, chromium steel 18/8 {GLO} market for steel, chromium steel 18/8 Cut-off, S	Ecoinvent 3	kg	2704,2
Titanium {GLO} market for titanium Cut-off, S	Ecoinvent 3	kg	287,53
Transport, freight, lorry 16-32 metric ton, EURO6 {RER} market for transport, freight, lorry 16-32 metric ton, EURO6 Cut-off, S	Ecoinvent 3	tkm	2090,929
Waste plastic, mixture {RER} market group for waste plastic, mixture Cut-off, S	Ecoinvent 3	kg	719,22

Supplementary: LCI thermoset EVTOL

Process	Database	Unit	Quantity
Aluminium (waste treatment) {GLO} recycling of aluminium Cut-off, S	Ecoinvent 3	kg	4780,27
Aluminium, primary, ingot {IAI Area, EU27 & EFTA} market for aluminium, primary, ingot Cut-off, S	Ecoinvent 3	kg	5031,86
Electricity, high voltage {Europe without Switzerland} market group for electricity, high voltage Cut-off, S	Ecoinvent 3	MJ	308962,1
Electricity, medium voltage {RER} market group for electricity, medium voltage Cut-off, S	Ecoinvent 3	MJ	1774903
Epoxy resin, liquid {RER} market for epoxy resin, liquid Cut-off, S	Ecoinvent 3	kg	576,58
Glass fibre {RER} glass fibre production Cut-off, S	Ecoinvent 3	kg	271,94
Polyacrylonitrile fibres (PAN), from acrylonitrile and methacrylate, prod. mix, PAN w/o additives EU-27 S	ELCD	kg	673,12
Steel and iron (waste treatment) {GLO} recycling of steel and iron Cut-off, S	Ecoinvent 3	kg	2760,68
Steel, chromium steel 18/8 {GLO} market for steel, chromium steel 18/8 Cut-off, S	Ecoinvent 3	kg	2704,2
Titanium {GLO} market for titanium Cut-off, S	Ecoinvent 3	kg	287,53
Transport, freight, lorry 16-32 metric ton, EURO6 {RER} market for transport, freight, lorry 16-32 metric ton, EURO6 Cut-off, S	Ecoinvent 3	tkm	2041,698
Waste asphalt {RoW} market for waste asphalt Cut-off, S	Ecoinvent 3	kg	390,17
Waste plastic, mixture {RER} market group for waste plastic, mixture Cut-off, S	Ecoinvent 3	kg	157,62

